

VARIATION IN COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OF CONCRETE BY PARTIAL REPLACEMENT OF CEMENT WITH MARBLE POWDER, SILICA FUMES AND LIME STONE POWDER

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Abstract:

Marble powder is a very fine powder, obtained as a by-product of marble during the sawing and the shaping. During the last decade, Lime stone powder as calcite, or crystalline $CaCO_3$, has proven to be an effective partial replacement for OPC [23]. Limestone is calcareous sedimentary rock composed of mineral calcite which upon calcination yields lime for commercial use. Silica fume is a byproduct of production of silicon metal or ferrosilicon alloys. One of the most beneficial uses for silica fume is in concrete. Because of its chemical and physical properties, it is a very reactive pozzolana. Concrete containing silica fume can have very high strength and can be very durable[.]. In this work the variation of compressive strength of concrete prepared by partial replacement of cement with marble powder, lime stone powder and silica fume were studied. Four types of mortar mixture with different cement replacement levels and water to cementitious materials ratio of 0.5 were prepared. The compressive strength of mortars and concretes are investigated at the ages of 7 days, 14 days and 28 days. It was observed that 28 days compressive strength of mortar was maximum for 10% replacement of cement by marble powder, 15% replacement of cement by lime stone powder and 22.5% replacement of cement by silica fume.

Keywords: Cement, Compressive strength, Waste Marble Powder, Silica fume, Lime stone powder

INTRODUCTION

The Indian marble industry has been growing steadily at an annual rate of around 10% per year. Cutting of stones produces heat, slurry, rock fragments and dust. 20 to 30% of marble blocks are converted in to powder. 3,172 thousand tons of marble dust was produced in year 2009-10.

The marble has been commonly used as a building material since ancient times. Disposal of the marble powder from the marble industry, consisting of very fine powder, is one of the environmental problems worldwide today. In this work, marble powder, obtained as a by-product of marble sawing and shaping, was characterized from a physical and chemical point of view for evaluating the possibility of using it in mortar and concrete production [1]. During the cutting process about 25% marble is resulted in dust [2]. Silica fume is a waste material that is products during the production of silicon and silicon alloys. silica fume is collected by filtering the gases escaping from furnace [3]. The addition of silica fume increases the rate of cement hydration at early hours due to release of OH^- ions and alkalis into pore fluids. This is attributable to the ability of silica fume to provide nucleating sites to hydration products like lime, calcium silicate hydrates (CSH) [4]. It has been reported that silica fume accelerates both C_3S and C_3A hydration during the first few hours [5].

Rao, G.A. [6] concluded that during the early ages, 3 and 7 days, strength of mortars with silica fume, in general, has been significantly high at any w/b ratio. The rate of strength development between 3 and 7 days was the highest. At w/b ratios 0.35, 0.40, and 0.45, the optimum silica fume contents for achieving highest compressive strength range between 17.5% and 22.5%.

Limestone in the lime industry is a general term for rocks that contain eighty percent or more calcium/magnesium carbonates including marble, chalk, oolite, and marl. The use of limestone powder can enhance many aspects of cement-based systems through physical or chemical effects. Some physical effects are associated with the small size of limestone particles, which can enhance the packing density of powder and reduce the interstitial void, thus decreasing entrapped water in the system.[7]

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Silica fume is a byproduct of producing silicon metal or ferrosilicon alloys. One of the most beneficial uses for silica fume is in concrete. It is a very reactive pozzolana. Concrete containing silica fume can have very high strength and can be very durable. Silica fume is available from suppliers of concrete admixtures and, when specified, is simply added during concrete production.

The use of wastes in concrete can reduce the consumption of natural resources and energy sources which in turn will further lessen the burden of pollutants on the environment.

Utilization of waste materials will reduce the cost of concrete production. Most of the previous research works reported are with ordinary Portland cement. The present research work is carried out with Portland pozzolana cement.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Carette.G & Malhotra V.M.(1983) reported results of an investigation on the early-age strength development of concrete incorporating 30% low-calcium fly ash, and to which small amounts of condensed silica fume have been added. The amount of silica fume 0-20% by combined weight of Portland cement and fly ash. A total of 30 m³ concrete mixture with water ratio of 0.40-0.80 were made. 240 cylinders were tested in compression and 180 prisms were tested in flexure. Test data showed that the incorporation of condensed silica fume increased the compressive strength of concrete at all ages as compared with the compressive strength of the control concrete (70% portland cement + 30% fly ash).

Verma A. ,Chandak R. , Yadav R.k.(2013) observed that characterization of silica fume and its effect on concrete with pozzolanic Portland cement. This paper deals with the influence of strength with addition of silica fume as an admixture to the concrete in various proportions 5%,10%,15%, and 20% by weight of cement. Concrete containing silica fume shows increase in strength up to 15%.

Sasila G., Kashyap A.M.N.(2014) investigate the effects of silica fume and Fly Ash additives on the Flexural Strength and durability of concrete. In this test silica fume and fly ash are used as cement replacement in proportions of 0, 5, 10, 15% by weight respectively. Flexural strength is tested after 7 and 28 days of the lime saturated water curing period. The experimental results indicate that using fly ash only decreases while silica fume increases 28-days flexural strength.

Experimental Investigation

The experimental investigation was planned to know the effect of marble powder, lime stone powder and silica fume additions as a replacement of Portland pozzolana cement. 6 types of mortar and 3 types of concrete were prepared. 7×7×7cm cube moulds are used for casting mortar samples and 15×15×15cm moulds are used for concrete samples. In mortar samples binder to fine aggregate ratio is 1:3. For concrete the M25 mix is designed as per IS 10262:2009.

Material used

1-Cement-Portland Pozzolana Cement (Mycem) Fly ash based conforming to (IS: 1489-1991) .The physical properties of cement obtained by conducting appropriate tests.

2-Fine aggregate- River sand is used & found to be Zone I its specific gravity is 2.60 & water absorption is 3.06% are given in table no.1.The grading curves of sand are shown in fig-1.

3-Coarse aggregate- Locally available 20 mm & 12.5mm size crushed granite.its specific gravity is 2.70 & water absorption is 1.24%.The grading curves of all aggregates are shown in Fig-2. The test results and requirements as per IS: 1489-1991

4-Water- Clean drinking fresh water (pH value 6-7) free from impurities used for concrete mixing.

5-Marble powder-Obtained from local marble processing plant out of sawing & polishing of marble blocks

6-Lime stone powder-Procured from Bawana Industrial plant

7-Silica fume-Delkem densified silica fume conforming to

IS-15388 :2003 procured from Delhi builder’s stores is used.

Table no-1: Physical properties of ingredient

Properties	Material	Test Results	Specifications
Fineness	Cement	5%	<10% Residue on Sieve no-9 2-4%
	Marble powder	24%	
	Lime stone powder	4.25%	
	Silica Fume	6%	
	Natural Sand	3.06%	
Specific Gravity	Cement	3.15	2.4-2.75 2.3-2.7 2.2-2.3 2.6-3.2
	Marble powder	2.5	
	Lime stone powder	2.61	
	Silica Fume	2.29	
	Fine aggregate	2.60	
	Coarse aggregate	2.70	
Setting Time(minutes) Initial Final	Cement	65	30 minutes (Min) 600 minutes (Max)
		405	
Water absorbtion	Fine aggregate	3%	
	Coarse aggregate	1.24%	
	Marble powder	0.75%	
	Lime stone powder	2.1%	
	Silica fume	3.4%	
Soundness	Cement	2 mm	10 mm (Max)
Impact value test	Coarse aggregate	14.85%	10-20%
Crushing value test	Coarse aggregate	17.71	
Compressive Strength (N/mm ²)	Cement		22 (N/mm ²) Min 27 (N/mm ²) Min 33 (N/mm ²) Min
	7 days	33	
	14 days	44	
	28 days	58	

Fig-1 Grading curve of Sand

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Fig-2 Grading curve of All in aggregate

Table No-2 : Details of Mortar Samples-% of Ingredients

S.No	SAMPLES	CEMENTITIOUS MATERIAL				FINE AGGREGATE		
		C	MP	LSP	SF	NS	MP	LSP
1	MP0	100				100		
2	MP5	95	5			100		
3	MP7.5	92.5	7.5			100		
4	MP10	90	10			100		
5	LSP10	90		10		100		
6	LSP15	85		15		100		
7	LSP20	80		20		100		
8	SF5	95			5	100		
9	SF10	90			10	100		
10	SF15	85			15	100		
11	SE17.5	82.5			17.5	100		
12	SF20	80			20	100		
13	SF22.5	77.5			22.5	100		
14	MP40	100				60	40	
15	MP45	100				55	45	
16	MP50	100				50	50	
17	MP55	100				45	55	
18	MLSP5	100				80	5	15
19	MLSP7.5	100				77.5	7.5	15
20	MLSP10	100				75	10	15

C- Cement , MP- Marble powder, LSP- Lime stone powder, SF- Silica fume, NS- Natural sand

Test Result on hardened Concrete

The compressive strength of different mortars with Cement is partially replaced by MP, LSP and SF at the ages of 7days, 14days, 28days are investigated and plotted in fig. No-3 to 6

The compressive strength of Concrete mixes obtained by casting cubes in 15 cm moulds. The cubes were compacted by means of standard vibration machine and plotted in fig No-7

Fig-3 Compressive strength % variation of MP

Fig-4 Compressive strength % variation of LSP

Fig-5 Compressive strength % variation of SF

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Fig-6 Compressive strength development of different mortars

Fig-7 Compressive strength development of different Concrete

CONCLUSION

- 1-The 7 days average compressive strength of concrete containing 10% MP and 17.5% SF was same as that of control mix.
- 2- The 7 days average compressive strength of concrete containing 15% LSP and 17.5% SF was same as that of control mix.
- 3- The 28 days average compressive strength of concrete containing 10% MP and 17.5% SF was increase by 4.60% compared to control mix.
- 4- The 28 days average compressive strength of concrete containing 15% LSP and 17.5% SF was increase by 4.60% compared to control mix.
- 5-Workability was increased by using small amount of marble powder as a replacement of cement.

6- The workability of green concrete remain unaffected by the percentage of lime stone powder ..

7-Workability of concrete improved with addition of silica fume .

8-Total percentage saving of cement in concrete with 10%MP and 17.5% silica fume is 27.5% and in concrete with 15% LSP and 17.5%SF is 32.5% .

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